

Prevalence and Predictors of Psychological Distress, Anxiety, and Depression among Hospitalized Covid-19 Patients in India

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ABSTRACT

Background: While the alarming rise of Covid-19 cases across world and particularly in India, the evidence-based studies on its impact on mental health of the symptomatic patients hospitalized for treatment are very few till date.

Aim: This study assessed the prevalence and predictors of depression, anxiety, psychological distress, and perceived social support in Covid-19 hospitalized patients.

Materials and Methods: It was a combination of online survey and offline regular survey. The Self-Reporting Questionnaire-20, Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale, and Multi-Dimensional Social Support Scale were used. Data collection was started from May 2, 2020 and closed on July 2, 2020. A total of 446 (M=356, F=90; Mean age=35.94 years) completed data sheets (response rate of 59.5%) were received from Covid-19 admitted patients in a tertiary care level hospital in Delhi-NCR.

Results: Prevalence rates of psychological distress, anxiety, and depression among Covid-19 hospitalized patients were found to be 12.56%, 17.49% and 19.28% respectively. Females, patients aged 31-45 years, and lower SES had significantly higher psychological distress as compared to their counterparts. Higher anxiety and depression scores, female gender and low SES were significant risk factors for psychological distress. Psychological distress and depression contributed positively hence were risk factors for increase in anxiety. And psychological distress, anxiety, male gender and lesser age were risk factors for increase in depression. 74% of total Covid-19 patients had high-perceived social support. Other findings were discussed in line with current literature

Conclusion: The findings suggested the prevalence of anxiety, depression and psychological distress to be mild to moderate among the Covid-19 patients. Clinical and Policy implication of all findings are highlighted.

Keywords: Anxiety, Depression, Psychological Distress, Social Support, Covid-19 Patients

INTRODUCTION

There is a consensus on the increase of the psychological burden and public's levels of anxiety-related symptoms in the eventuality of any major infectious pandemic disease occurred in the past such as by SARS (Su et al., 2007) and MERS (Lee et al., 2018). Various such studies also reported mental health problems (Lee et al., 2007; Lu et al., 2006; McAlonan et al., 2007) in general in addition to post-traumatic stress disorder and poor sleep (Kobayashi et al., 2007) and depression was found to be the most prevalent (Mak et al., 2009).

Since the beginning of 2020, the enhancement of knowledge on varied clinical manifestation of the nCov-19 virus, better treatment-management modalities, improved medication, and control of worsening factors is appreciable in terms of improved health outcomes and reducing death rate. However, recent studies on mental health impacts of Covid-19 reported the overall prevalence of GAD (one in three participants-35.1%), depressive symptoms (one in five participants- 20.1%), and sleep quality (18.2%), during COVID-19 (Huang and Zhao, 2020). A Chinese study with

1210 sample from 194 cities reported moderate or severe intensity of psychological impact (53.8%), anxiety (28.8%), depression (16.5%) and stress levels (8.1%) in the participants (Wang et al, 2020a). Females and those who had poor perceived health status reported significantly higher stress, anxiety, and depression. The prevalence of anxiety was in 6.33% and depression in 17.17% respectively in another study reported from China (Wang et al, 2020b). A study from Argentina revealed raised symptoms of depression (27.5%), phobia (41.3%), anxiety (31.8%), obsessive-compulsive behaviours (25.1%) distress in general (27.1%), and Hostility (13.7%) during quarantined period (Fernández, et.al., 2020). A recent Indian online survey among general population (N=1871) reported that 38.2% had anxiety, 10.5% reported depression, however, 40.5% had either anxiety or depression. Further, 74.1% experienced moderate level of stress and 71.7% had poor well-being due to pandemic situation (Grover et.al., 2020). Nevertheless, these are studies primarily on general public and/or health workers. Similarly, in a sample of, another online survey reported

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23.6% (n=81) had self-reported depression and 45.1% (n=155) had self-reported anxiety (Özdin & Özdin, 2020).

Extrapolating from the findings on impact of Covid-19 on general public, it would be prudent enough to anticipate heightened fear, uncertainty, and other negative mental health consequences among the Covid-19 positive and hospitalized patients as the Covid-19 situation is still grim with continuing uncertainty related health outcomes, fear of death/relapse/infecting others, and stigma among public across the world. A recent study with a small sample size (N=61 from Pakistan) reported that a majority (72.1-75.4%) fell within the normal anxiety and stress category. Females experienced significantly higher level of depression, anxiety and stress than males (Raza et al, 2020). Few studies from China reported findings on prevalence of anxiety and depression to be high, although with different assessment tools. While using Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (HADS) one study reported the prevalence of self-reported anxiety to be 34.72% and depression to be 28.47% among Covid-19 positive cases (N=144) (Dong et al, 2020), the other study (N=85) by using (PHQ-9 \geq 5) revealed self-reported depression among 45.9% and 38.8% had anxiety (GAD-7 \geq 5) (Hu et al, 2020). Even Covid-19 patients have been found with neurological and neuro-psychiatric complications, such as over a 3-week period, 39 (31%) patients had altered mental status (Varatharaj et al., 2020; Ellul et al., 2020). In addition, Covid-19 can also result in adverse impact on patients with existing mental illness. For example, schizophrenia patients (N=21) suspected and admitted for Covid-19 reported statistically higher stress, depression, anxiety, and poor sleep quality as compared to schizophrenia patients without Covid-19 (N=158) in China. (Liu et.al., 2020). Given the small sample size, the prevalence of important mental health indicators and the risk factors are not well understood. The cultural differences, especially the health care facilities and affordability of Covid-10 specific health care and treatment can bring out lot of changes in the prevalence of mental health indicators. We did a thorough search in PubMed and Google Scholar databases and to our knowledge, apart from the studies included here, no other study on mental health of Covid-19 hospitalized patients is available on till 10th of August 2020. Moreover, not a single study from India is reported on psychological health status of Covid-19 hospitalized patients, therefore, making it imperative to report the findings.

Objectives: Firstly, the study assessed the mental health status and perceived social support of Covid-19 patients during the hospitalization period. Secondly, it examined the factors in prevalence of depression, anxiety, and psychological distress. Thirdly, it attempted to find out the age and gender differences in the prevalence rate of these mental health indicators.

MATERIALS & METHODS

The study had adopted a prospective observational research design to recruit hospitalized Covid-19 patients from a tertiary care level hospital in Delhi-NCR (Ethics approval No-IEC-320/27.04.2020, RP 14/2020). Although, the study was initially planned for an online survey using Google Forms circulated through the WhatsApp number of Covid-19 patients from the hospital list, the patients were given

options for both on-line and offline survey. All the tools were available in Hindi and English, and 3 psychiatry post-graduate and senior residents following WHO back translation method did the translation into Tamil. The Google Form was designed in such a way that unless all mandatory items are not filled in it would not allow submission, and only 1 form can be submitted from one number.

Demographic and Brief Clinical Profile

A socio-demographic and brief clinical profile sheet including information on age, gender, marital status, educational qualifications, socio-economic status, job details, history of any pre-existing mental illness in patient before Covid-19, history of mental illness in family members, history of Covid-19 patients in own family/relatives, history of death due to Covid-19, current feelings, etc. was done.

Sample & Sampling:

A convenient sampling method was adopted following inclusion and exclusion parameters as mentioned below:

Inclusion criteria:

- a. Male & female adults
- b. Conscious COVID-19 patients hospitalized for treatment (Covid-19 patients with mild to moderate symptoms not requiring ICU care)
- c. Comorbid health conditions

Exclusion criteria:

- d. Patients on ventilators
- e. Not consenting to participate

Tools used:

Self-Reporting Questionnaire (SRQ -20) (Beusenberg and Orley 1994): A total of 20 dichotomous (true or false) items assessing psychological distress was included. Researchers have adapted the SRQ to a variety of settings and have validated that it is able to detect common mental disorders across cultural contexts with reasonable accuracy across the world.

Hospital Anxiety & Depression Scale-(HADS):

This scale (Snath and Zigmond, 1986) contains 14 questions, including 7 each for rating anxiety and depression. The interpretation criteria were same for both the subscales (Normal:0-7, suggestive of presence of depression/anxiety: 8-10, probable presence of depression/anxiety at disorder level: \geq 11). Hindi and Tamil versions were used where needed, though these have not been validated earlier.

Multidimensional Scale for Perceived Social Support (MSPSS) (Zimet, Dahlem, Zimet, and Farley, 1988):

MSPSS is a 12 itemed self-reported psychometrically sound measure of the subjective assessment of the adequacy of received emotional and social support from family, friends and other important people. Each of these three dimensions is assessed with four items on a 7-point Likert type scale (1= very strongly disagree to 7= very strongly agree). A mean scale score between 1-2.9 indicates low support; between 3- 5 is considered as moderate support; and between 5.1-7 indicates high support. The test-retest reliability of MSPSS for friends; family and significant others were .85, .75, and .72 respectively. Assessment of

internal consistency of the MSPSS, via Cronbach's coefficient alpha has been reported by a number of researchers ranging from .77 to .92. Higher score indicated higher perceived social support.

RESULTS

In total, 750 conscious Covid-19 hospitalized patients in a tertiary care level hospital in Delhi-NCR were approached through telephone during 2nd May-2nd July 2020. All of them were given the option of completing the data either online (Google Form sent through WhatsApp) or offline. The study included tools in English, Hindi, and Tamil. Tamil translation and back translation was done by 3 independent residents of Dept. of Psychiatry whose mother tongue was Tamil. A total of 737 patients consented to participate out of which only 13 people completed online data and 724 completed hard copies of data sheets. However, only 446 data sheets complete in all respects were included here for analysis (Excluded= 232 data sheets due to at least one incomplete filled-in or missing scale, 50 invalid data sheets only with filled in socio-demographic without any filled in scale or some items filled in, and 9 data sheets on age criteria (below 18 and above 60 years), thus 291 were excluded. Thus, with a response rate of 59.5%, the final sample included 446 Covid-19 hospitalized patients (Male=356- 78.5% & Female=90- 21.5%) with a mean age of 35.94 (SD=11.71) with mild to moderate Covid-19 symptoms. A total of 290 (65%) were currently married/in a relationship, 247 (55.4%) had below bachelor's degree of education, 292 (65.2%) had full-time job, and 293 (65.7%) belonged to middle socio-income status (Table-1).

Table-1: Demographic and Clinical Profile of Covid-19 Patients

N=446 (100%)	
Age groups (Mean Age = 35.94; SD=11.71)	
18-30 years=174(39%); 31-45 years=165 (37%)	
46-60 years= 96 (21.5%); Above 60 year= 11 (2.5%)	
Sex: Male= 350 (78.5%) ; Female= 96 (21.5%)	
Relationship Status	
Currently married/in a relationship =290 (65%) ; Single= 156 (35%)	
Education status	
Below bachelor's degree=247 (55.4%)	
≥ Bachelor's degree and above=199 (44.6%)	
Employment status	
No fulltime job=154 (34.5%); Fulltime job=292 (65.2%)	
Socio-economic status	
Upper= 30 (6.7%); Middle= 293 (65.7%); Lower= 123 (27.6%)	
Accompanying chronic disease	
Yes=88 (19.7%); No=358 (80.3%)	
Covid-19 in other Family members	
Yes= 132 (29.6%) ; No=314 (70.4%)	
Death due to Covid-19 in family/relatives	
Yes=14(3.1%) ;No=432 (96.9%)	
Death due to other reasons during Covid-19	
Yes= 15 (3.4%); No=431 (96.6%)	
Family history of Mental illness	
Yes=5 (1.1) ; No=441 (98.9%)	

Self-Reporting Questionnaire-20

Table-2 presented that the prevalence of psychological distress on SRQ-20 among Covid-19 hospitalized patients was found to be around 12.56% as per Indian cut off value (Deshpande et al., 1989) of 8 and above. It was revealed from Table-3 that while 8.9% males were above cutoff on SRQ, 26% of female Covid-19 patients were above the SRQ cut off for Indian population. Table-4 revealed that the males (Mean=2.24, SD=2.78) and females (Mean=3.96, SD=4.53) differed significantly in reporting psychological distress (t=4.58, p<0.00). Significant mean difference (t'= 2.21, p< 0.02) was found between the SRQ score of Covid-19 patients aged 31-45 years (n=165, Mean=3.05 SD=3.69) and 46-60 years (n=96, Mean=2.05 SD=3.21). The mean SRQ score of patients in lower SES (Mean=3.5, SD=3.64) was significantly higher (F=7.88, p<0.00) than the patients either in middle (Mean=2.36, SD=3.19) or in upper SES (Mean= 1.30, SD=2.00). Thus, these findings suggested that females, patients aged between 31-45 years, and lower SES had significantly higher psychological distress as compared to their counterparts.

Table-2: Severity on SRQ, HADS, and MPSSS

Variables	
Self-reporting Questionnaire (SRQ)	Above Cutoff n= 56 (12.56%); M = 9.50 SD=2.7 Below Cutoff n=390 (87.44%); M=1.62, SD=1.90
Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale-Depression: HADS D	Normal n= 360 (80.72%); M = 2.95 SD= 2.25 Mild n= 61 (13.68%); M= 8.66, SD=.772 Moderate n= (5.38%); 24 M = 11.96, SD= 1.16 Severe n=1 (0.3%); M= 15
Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale-Anxiety: HADS A	Normal n= 368 (82.51%); M= 2.96, SD= 2.25 Mild n= 54 (12.1%); M= 8.91, SD= .806 Moderate n= 23 (5.2%); M= 12.22, SD=.998 Severe n= 1 (0.3%); M= 16.00
Multidimensional Perceived Social Support Scale: MPSSS	Mean = 5.50, SD= 1.50 Low Support= 37 (8.3%) Moderate Support= 79 (17.7%) High Support= 330 (74%)

Table-5 presented the findings of the stepwise regression model for SRQ, which was significant (F= 263.18; Sig= 0.000) with an R² of 0.455 indicating that the model has satisfactory explanation power for explaining the SRQ scores. Findings of a regression analysis revealed that HADS A (β = .61, p = .000), HADS D (β = .24, p = .000), gender (β = .19, p = .000), and socio-economic status (β = -.11, p =.002) were found to be as significant risk factors to predict psychological distress. Although HADS anxiety contributed 61% of variance alone, combined with HADS depression they together contributed 71%, thus, 10% variance was added alone by HADS anxiety of the Covid-19 patients. Similarly, another 18% of variance was contributed by gender, thus making the total variance to 89%. SES contributed another 11% variance to SRQ. While HADS anxiety, HADS depression, and gender contributed positively, SES contributed negatively to psychological distress of the Covid-19 patients. This implied that that rise in HADS anxiety and depression scores increased psychological distress in the respondents and female gender and low SES were risk factors for psychological distress.

Table-3: Mental Health Profile across Socio-demographic variables

	HADS (A)				HADS (D)				SRQ			MPSS	
	Normal f (%)	Mild f (%)	Moderate f (%)	Severe f (%)	Normal f (%)	Mild f (%)	Moderate f (%)	Severe f (%)	Above Cutoff f (%)	Below Cutoff f (%)	Low SS f (%)	Moderate SS f (%)	High SS f (%)
Male	297 (84.9%)	39 (11.1%)	13 (3.7%)	1 (.3%)	280(80%)	50 (14.3%)	19 (5.4%)	1 (.3%)	31 (8.9%)	319 (91.1%)	4 (6.9%)	59 (16.9%)	267(76.3%)
Female	71 (74%)	15 (15.6%)	10(10.4%)	Nil	80 (83.3%)	11 (11.5%)	5 (5.2%)	Nil	25 (26%)	71 (74%)	13(13.5)	20(20.8%)	63 (65%)
16-30yrs.	145 (83.3%)	22(12.6%)	6(3.4%)	1(.6%)	139(79.9%)	26(14.9%)	9(5.2%)	Nil	20(11.5%)	154(88.5%)	17(9.8%)	33(19%)	124(71.3%)
31-45 yrs.	136(82.4%)	16(9.7%)	13(7.9%)	Nil	126(76.4%)	27(16.4%)	11(6.7%)	1(.6%)	26(15.8%)	139(84.2%)	11(6.7%)	28(17%)	126(76.4%)
46-60 yrs.	79(82.3%)	14(14.6%)	3(3.1%)	Nil	85(88.5%)	7(7.3%)	4(4.2%)	Nil	8(8.3%)	88(91.7%)	8(8.3%)	16(16.7%)	72((75%)
Above 60	8(72.7%)	2(18.2%)	1(9.1%)	Nil	10(90.9%)	1(9.1%)	Nil	Nil	2(18.2%)	9(81.8%)	1(9.1%)	2(18.2%)	8(72.7%)
Married	239(82.4%)	35 (12.1%)	15 (5.2%)	1(.3%)	241 (83.1%)	34 (11.7%)	15 (5.2%)	Nil	33 (11.4%)	257 (88.6%)	20(6.9%)	50(17.2%)	220(75.9%)
Single	129 (82.7%)	19 (12.2%)	8 (5.1%)	Nil	119 (76.3%)	27 (17.3%)	9 (5.8%)	1 (.6%)	23 (14.7%)	133 (85.3%)	17(10.9)	29(18.6%)	110(70.5%)
<Bachelors	200 (81%)	32 (13%)	15(6.1%)	Nil	188 (76.1%)	38 (15.4%)	20 (8.1%)	1 (.4%)	36 (14.6%)	211 (85.4%)	21(8.5%)	47(19%)	179(72.5%)
≥Bachelors	168 (84.4%)	22 (11.1%)	8 (4%)	Nil	172 (86.4%)	23 (11.6%)	4 (2%)	Nil	20 (10.1%)	179 (89.9%)	16(8%)	32(16.1%)	151(75.9%)
Low SES	90(73.2%)	22 (17.9%)	11 (8.9%)	Nil	88 (71.5%)	23 (18.7%)	11 (8.9%)	1 (.8%)	24 (19.5%)	99 (80.5%)	8(6.5%)	19(15.4%)	96(78%)
Middle SES	253(86.3%)	29 (9.9%)	10 (3.4%)	Nil	247 (84.3%)	34 (11.6%)	12 (4.1%)	Nil	31 (10.6%)	262 (89.4%)	27(9.2%)	52(17.7%)	214(73%)
Upper SES	25 (83.3%)	3 (10%)	2(6.7%)	Nil	25 (83.3%)	4 (13.3%)	1 (3.3%)	Nil	1 (3.3)	29 (96.7)	2(6.7%)	8(26.7%)	20(66.7%)

Note: Abbreviations: SES-socio-economic status, HADS-Hospital anxiety and depression scale, (A)-Anxiety, (D)-Depression, SRQ- Self-report questionnaire, MPSSS-Multidimensional perceived social support scale.

Table-4: Mean differences on SRQ, HADS, and MPSSS

	HADS (A)			HADS (D)			SRQ			MPSSS		
	Mean & SD	T test/F test	P Value	Mean & SD	T test/F test	P Value	Mean & SD	T test/F test	P Value	Mean & SD	T test/F test	P Value
Male (N=350)	M=4.08 SD=3.31	T =1.24	.216	M=4.27 SD=3.51	T = .303	.762	M=2.24 SD=2.78	T =4.58	.00	M=5.58 SD=1.43	T=2.30	.02
Female (N=96)	M=4.57 SD=3.51			M=4.15 SD=3.13			M=3.96 SD=4.53			M=5.19 SD=1.69		
18-30yrs. (N=174)	M= 4.34 SD=3.33	F=.468	.705	M=4.28 SD=3.39	F=.604	.612	M=2.44 SD=2.91	F=2.26	.08	M=5.54 SD=1.57	F=.142	.935
31-45 yrs. (N= 165)	M=4.21 SD= 3.66			M=4.43 SD=3.66			M=3.05 SD=3.69	(T test between group 2 and 3)	.02	M=5.53 SD=1.44		
46-60 yrs. (N=96)	M=3.83 SD=3.45			M=3.84 SD=3.10			M=2.05 SD=3.21	T=2.21		M=5.55 SD=1.37		
Above 60 (N=11)	M=4.36 SD=3.93			M=4.18 SD=3.18			M=3.36 SD=3.50			M=5.37 SD=1.50		
Married (N=290)	M=4.14 SD=3.53	T = .373	.71	M=4.05 SD=3.32	T= 1.58	.114	M=2.40 SD=2.40	T=1.79	.07	M=5.59 SD=1.46	T=1.79	.07
Single (N=156)	M=4.27 SD=3.30			M=4.59 SD= 3.59			M=2.99 SD= 3.55			M=5.32 SD=1.55		
<Bachelors (N=247)	M=4.40 SD=3.44	T= 1.30	.191	M=4.55 SD=3.17	T= 2.11	.03	M=2.79 SD=3.37	T=1.43	.151	M=5.50 SD=1.53	T=.003	.998
≥Bachelors (N=199)	M=3.92 SD=3.45			M=3.86 Sd=3.0			M=2.38 SD=3.22			M=5.50 SD=1.46		
Low SES (N=123)	M=5.07 SD=3.71	F=5.77	.003	M=4.85 SD=3.93	F=2.67	.07	M=3.50 SD=3.64	F=7.88	.000	M=5.59 SD=1.45	F=.298	.742
Middle SES (N=239)	M=3.87 SD=3.28			M=4.00 SD=3.18			M=2.36 SD=3.19			M=5.46 SD=1.54		
Upper SES (N= 30)	M=3.67 SD=3.37			M=4.07 SD=3.31			M=1.30 SD=2.00			M=5.48 SD=1.32		

Note: Abbreviations: SES-socio-economic status, HADS-Hospital anxiety and depression scale, (A)-Anxiety, (D)-Depression, SRQ- Self-report questionnaire, MPSSS-Multidimensional perceived social support scale.

Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale (and 3)

Table-2 showed that more than 80% of patients were in the normal range of both anxiety and depression subscales of HADS. Thus, the prevalence rate of anxiety and depression screened on HADS was found to be 17.49% and 19.28% respectively. For the total sample, the prevalence rate of mild (12.1%), moderate (5.1%) and severe (0.3%) anxiety; and the prevalence rate of mild (13.68%), moderate (5.38%), and severe depression (0.3%) was reported. Interestingly, anxiety was more prevalent in female (26%) as compared to 12.1% male patients, whereas depression was prevalent more in male (20%) as compared to 16.7% of female patients. However, Table-4 indicated that males and females did not differ significantly on any subscales of HADS.

Table 5: Stepwise Linear Regression on Self-Reporting Questionnaire (SRQ)

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient		Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
(Constant)	.155	.196		.790	.430
HADS (A)	.585	.036	.61	16.223	.000
HADS (A) & HADS (D)	.448	.044	.47	10.121	.000
	.227	.045	.24	5.084	.000
HADS (A), HADS (D), & gender	.429	.043	.45	9.937	.000
	.241	.043	.25	5.566	.000
	1.528	.287	.19	5.326	.000
HADS (A), HADS (D), gender, & SES	.412	.043	.43	9.577	.000
	.241	.043	.25	5.622	.000
	1.610	.285	.20	5.645	.000
	-.689	.216	-.11	-3.193	.002

Dependent Variable: SRQ; R²: 0.455

Note: Abbreviations: SES-socio-economic status, HADS-Hospital anxiety and depression scale, (A)-Anxiety, (D)-Depression, SRQ- Self-report questionnaire.

According to Table-3, prevalence of mild anxiety was highest in patients aged 46-60 years (Mild-14.6% and moderate-3.1%) followed by the patients' aged 18-30years (Mild -12.6%, moderate-3.4%, and severe- 0.6%) and 31-45 years (Mild- 9.7% and moderate-7.9%) Although, the prevalence was highest for patients above 60 years (Mild-18.2% and Moderate-9.1%), as the sample size was small the findings can be read cautiously. Prevalence of mild depression was found to be highest in the age group of 31-45 years (16.4%) followed by 18-30 years (14.9%), ≥60 (9.1%) and 46-60 (7.3%). In addition, prevalence of moderate depression was also highest (6.7%) for patients aged between 31-45 years.

Interestingly, table-3 also revealed that the prevalence of mild and moderate anxiety among the currently married/in relationship (Mild-12.1%, moderate- 5.2%) and those who were single/not in any relationship (Mild-12.2%, moderate-5.1%) was almost equal. And the prevalence of mild and moderate depression was more among the currently single/not in a relationship (Mild-17.3%, moderate-5.8%, severe-0.6%) as compared to the patients who were married or in a relationship (Mild-11.7% and moderate-5.2%).

It was found from table-3 that, mild anxiety was marginally more prevalent among patients who had lesser educational qualifications (Mild-13%, moderate 6.1%, and severe-0.5%) as compared to patients (Mild-11.1% and moderate-4%) who had graduation and above educational qualifications. Table-4 presented the mean HADS depression score of patients who were not graduates (Mean=4.55, SD=3.17) to be significantly higher (t=2.11, p<0.03) than the patients were graduates and above. Thus, it implied that less educated Covid-19 patients had significantly higher levels of depression as compared to their higher educated counterparts.

Lastly, Table-3 indicated that patients in lower socio-economic status (SES) reported higher prevalence of mild (17.9%) and moderate (8.9%) anxiety as compared to patients belonged to middle (mild-9.9% and moderate-3.4%) and upper (mild-10% and moderate-6.7%) SES. Similarly, prevalence of mild depression was highest among patients in lower (18.7%) followed by upper (13.3%) and middle (11.6%) SES. Table-4 revealed that the mean HADS anxiety score of patients in lower SES (Mean=5.07, SD=3.71) was significantly higher (F=5.77, p<0.003) than the patients either in middle (Mean=3.87, SD=3.28) or in upper SES (Mean= 3.67, SD=3.37). Thus, it indicated significantly higher anxiety in lower SES as compared to middle and upper SES.

Table-6: Stepwise Regression on HADS Anxiety

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	
	B	Std. Error				
1	(Constant)	2.530	.165		15.331	.000
	SRQ	.636	.039	.610	16.223	.000
	(Constant)	1.386	.187		7.398	.000
2	SRQ	.419	.041	.402	10.121	.000
	HADS (D)	.403	.040	.401	10.082	.000

Dependent variable: HADS A; R²=0.489

Note: Abbreviations: HADS-Hospital anxiety and depression scale, (A)-Anxiety, (D)-Depression, SRQ- Self-report questionnaire.

Table-6 presented the findings of the stepwise regression model for anxiety domain in HADS, which was significant (F= 263.82; Sig= 0.000) with an R² of 0.489 indicating that the model had satisfactory explanation power for explaining the HADS anxiety scores. Thus, according to the findings of multiple linear regression analysis evaluating risk factors for anxiety, SRQ or psychological distress (β =.61, p = .000), and HADS D (β = .40, p = .000) were found to predict higher anxiety in Covid-19 patients. Although SRQ contributed 61% of variance alone, combined with HADS depression they together contributed 80%, thus, 19% variance was added alone by HADS depression of the Covid-19 patients. Both SRQ and HADS depression contributed positively to anxiety of the Covid-19 patients. This implied that that rise in psychological distress and depression scores increased anxiety in the respondents thus, were risk factors for increase in anxiety.

According to the findings presented in Table-7, the stepwise regression model for depression domain in HADS, which was significant (F= 262.18; Sig= 0.000) with an R² of 0.421

indicating that the model had satisfactory explanation power for explaining the HADS depression scores. Thus, HADS anxiety ($\beta = .61, p = .000$), SRQ ($\beta = .24, p = .000$), Gender ($\beta = - 0.1, p = .000$) and Age ($\beta = -.01, p = .000$) were found to predict higher depression in Covid-19 patients. While SRQ and HADS anxiety contributed positively to depression of the Covid-19 patients, gender and age contributed negatively. Importantly, male gender and lesser age were risk factors for increase in depression.

Table 7: Stepwise Regression on HADS Depression

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.705	.203		8.409	.000
HADS (A)	.605	.037	.609	16.192	.000
2 HADS (A)	.463	.046	.466	10.082	.000
SRQ	.243	.048	.235	5.084	.000
3 HADS (A)	.452	.046	.455	9.867	.000
SRQ	.272	.049	.262	5.566	.000
Gender	-.807	.312	-.097	-2.590	.010
4 HADS (A)	.455	.046	.458	9.972	.000
SRQ	.265	.049	.256	5.436	.000
Gender	-.901	.314	-.108	-2.874	.004
Age	-.482	.227	-.078	-2.126	.034

Dependent Variable: HADS(D); $R^2=0.421$

Note: Abbreviations: HADS-Hospital anxiety and depression scale, (A)-Anxiety, (D)-Depression, SRQ- Self-report questionnaire

The correlation analysis between age and HADS depression also revealed the same trend suggesting that increase in age was associated with decrease in depression ($r = -.12, p < 0.01$).

Table 8: Stepwise Regression on MPSSS

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	68.590	1.070		64.087	.000
SRQ	-.985	.254	-.181	-3.877	.000

Dependent Variable: MPSSS; $R^2=0.033$

Note: Abbreviations: SRQ- Self-report questionnaire, MPSSS-Multidimensional perceived social support scale.

Perceived Social Support

Table-2 revealed that a significant section of total Covid-19 patients (74%) was found to have high-perceived social support with a mean of 5.50. This was followed by low (8.3%) and moderate social support (17.7%). Table-3 revealed that while 76.3% of males had perceived higher followed by moderate (16.9%) and low (6.9%) social support, 65% of females perceived high social support followed by 20.8% perceived moderate and 13.5% perceived low social support. Table-4 showed males (Mean=5.58, SD=1.43) perceiving significantly higher ($t'=2.30, p < 0.02$) amount of social support available to them during the Covid-19 hospitalization as compared to the female (Mean 5.19, SD=1.69) patients. The correlation

analysis suggested a significant negative association with anxiety ($r = -.172, p < 0.01$) and depression ($r = -.11, p < 0.05$) on HADS. This further indicated that increased social support decreased both anxiety and depression.

Social support did not emerge as a significant predictor of psychological distress, anxiety, and depression. However, stepwise regression model for perceived social support indicated psychological distress as measured through SRQ was the only significant ($F = 15.033; Sig = 0.000$) predictor of perceived social support with an R^2 of 0.033 indicating that the model had satisfactory explanation power for explaining the MPSSS scores (Table-8). The findings evaluating risk factors for perceived social support indicated psychological distress ($\beta = -.18, p = .000$) as a significant predictor. The negative contribution of SRQ towards perceived social support suggested that higher psychological distress was risk factor for lower social support.

Summary of Key Findings

1. The sample consisted of 78.5% males and 21.5% females.
2. The average age was 35.94 years for the sample.
3. Prevalence rates of psychological distress, anxiety, and depression among Covid-19 hospitalized patients were found to be 12.56%, 17.49% and 19.28% respectively.
4. Females, patients aged 31-45 years, and lower SES had significantly higher psychological distress as compared to their counterparts. Higher HADS anxiety and depression scores, female gender and low SES were significant risk factors for psychological distress.
5. The prevalence rate of mild, moderate and severe anxiety was 12.1%, 5.1%, and 0.3% respectively; and the prevalence rate of mild, moderate, and severe depression was 13.68%, 5.38%, and 0.3% respectively for the total sample. Interestingly, anxiety was more prevalent in female (26% vs 12.1%) patients, whereas depression was prevalent more in male (20% vs 16.7%) patients. However, males and females had statistically same levels of anxiety or depression on HADS.
6. While Covid-19 patients with lower education were significantly more depressed than the patients with graduation and above education, significantly higher anxiety was present in lower SES as compared to middle and upper SES.
7. Regression analysis revealed that psychological distress and depression contributed positively, hence were risk factors for increase in anxiety. However, psychological distress, anxiety, male gender and lesser age were risk factors for increase in depression.
8. A significant section of total Covid-19 patients (74%) was found to have high-perceived social support. Males perceived significantly higher social support available to them during the Covid-19 hospitalization as compared to the female patients. Increased social support was correlated significantly with decreased anxiety and depression. Nevertheless, higher

psychological distress was risk factor for lower social support.

DISCUSSION

The sample had a more than 3 times males (78.5%) than female (21.5). The average age was 35.94. This finding is as per the existing literature supporting Covid-19 affecting more males than females and the average age of covid-19 patients to be around 35-40.

Prevalence rates of psychological distress, anxiety, and depression among Covid-19 hospitalized patients were found to be 12.56%, 17.49% and 19.28% respectively. Although the reported studies on prevalence of anxiety and depression among the public during Covid-19 period (35.1% and 20.1% respectively in Huang and Zhao, 2020); and health care workers directly working with Covid-19 patients (Jianbo et al., 2020); and Covid-19 patients (especially 34.72% and 28.47% respectively on HADS by Dong et al, 2020; and 45.9% reported depression (PHQ-9 \geq 5), and 38.8% had anxiety (GAD-7 \geq 5) (Hu et al, 2020) the prevalence rate was remarkably less in our study. This could be explained in terms of small sample size of Covid-19 patients (two studies had <100 Covid-19 patients and one had <150 sample), and mixture of hospitalized and non-hospitalized Covid-19 patients participated in those studies.

Females, patients aged 31-45 years, and lower SES had significantly higher psychological distress. This finding on females was similar to a study reported from Pakistan (Rza et al, 2020) which suggested that higher HADS anxiety and depression scores, female gender and low SES were significant risk factors for psychological distress. If we extrapolate findings of a study done on general public during Covid-19 (Wang, Di, Ye, and Wei, 2020) reporting people \leq 40 years old had an increased risk of anxiety than those more than 40 years. Thus, younger people had perhaps less anxiety handling ability, which can result in more psychological distress.

The mild, moderate and severe anxiety prevalence rate were 12.1%, 5.1%, and 0.3% respectively; and depression prevalence was 13.68%, 5.38%, and 0.3% respectively for the total sample. Interestingly, anxiety was more prevalent in female (26% vs 12.1%) patients, whereas depression was prevalent more in male (20% vs 16.7%) patients. This finding could be attributed to the fact that women in general have intense involvements in performing their social, household, and caregiving roles which can elevate the stress level and ultimately women are more prone to anxiety. And being hospitalized due to Covid-19 could have affected their homes, family, and social role more adversely, which could have resulted in more anxiety. Prevalence of anxiety more in females in our study could lay its support to an earlier study (Wang, Di, Ye, and Wei, 2020) reporting female anxiety risk to be 3.01 times higher than males among common public during Covid-19 epidemic. However, there was no statistically significant difference they were similar in terms of their experience of anxiety and depression.

The finding of Covid-19 patients with lower education found to be significantly more depressed than the patients with graduation and above education was contrast to a study reporting highly educated people were more depressed

during Covid-19 epidemic (Wang, Di, Ye, and Wei, 2020). The finding of significantly higher anxiety was present in lower SES as compared to middle and upper SES was in line of a recent study reporting consistent association of social determinants such as poverty with more Covid-19 vulnerability and morbidity (Yancy, 2020).

Regression analysis revealed that psychological distress and depression contributed positively, hence were risk factors for increase in anxiety. However, psychological distress, anxiety, male gender and younger age were risk factors for increase in depression. Our finding was partially corroborated with a study reporting gender, age, and social support were associated with anxiety for COVID-19 patients; and age, family infection with SARS and social support ($\beta = -2.236$, $p < 0.001$) were the risk factors for depression (Dong et al, 2020). Negative effects of hypochondriasis and higher anxiety perhaps affected overall health and well-being of people at risk of the epidemic (Duncan et al. 2009; Pappas et al. 2009; Ropeik 2004). A part of this finding is contradictory to a recently published paper (Jianbo et al., 2020) reporting female gender was at higher risk of severe symptoms all such mental conditions and symptoms. This difference could be attributed to difference in sample (Covid-19 hospitalized patients in our study vs health care workers), scales used to screen (HADS in our study vs PHQ-9 and GAD-7) and sample constituent (Males constituted more than 75% of sample in our study vs females constituted more than 75%). Further the younger age group was more vulnerable to depression was also supported by Huang and Zhao (2020) study on prevalence of depression among public.

A significant section of total Covid-19 patients (74%) was found to have high-perceived social support. Males perceived significantly higher social support available to them during the Covid-19 hospitalization as compared to the female patients. Increased social support was correlated significantly with decreased anxiety and depression. Nevertheless, higher psychological distress was risk factor for lower social support. Our findings were similar to earlier studies reporting social support to have a positive role in reducing anxiety of people under stress, thus decreasing psychological distress [Xiao, 2020, Jacobson, Lord, Newman, 2017]. Studies have found that low levels of social support are potential risks factors of developing depression and anxiety symptoms in the eventuality of stress exposure [Guntzviller, Williamson, Ratcliff, 2020], and that social support can be an important contributor to promote mental health [Gu, et al, 2016] even when the stressor is being a hospitalized of Covid-19 pandemic.

In nutshell, as contrast to reported studies done among public and health workers in Covid-19 epidemic, the anxiety, depression, and psychological distress prevalence rate in our study came out to be mild-to-moderate among the Covid-19 hospitalized patients. However, this is in line of a recent study with a small sample size (N=61 from Pakistan) reported that a significant portion of Covid-19 patients i.e., 72.1% reported depression and 75.4% fell within the normal anxiety and stress category (Rza et al, 2020). This was a very crucial finding, and this could be due to reason that the entire hospital stay and treatment (boarding, lodging, medication, treatment, other services)

are free of cost for all patients (irrespective of status of health insurance) receiving treatment at public hospitals in India. This might have reduced significant amount of anxiety and psychological distress among the patients. In other words, zero financial burden for all patients might have acted as a strong social support mechanism, hence buffering anxiety, depression, and psychological distress. More than 80% of our Covid-19 patients were within the normal range of anxiety, depression, and psychological distress. As per a systematic review and meta-analysis (Rogers et al., 2020), similar to SARS or MERS, recovery of Covid-19 patients may not lead to significant mental health conditions. However, the possibility of depression, anxiety, fatigue, post-traumatic stress, poor sleep quality, irritability, and rarer longer term neuropsychiatric problems cannot be clinically ruled out, hence clinician's vigilance for such conditions is required.

LIMITATIONS

This study had few limitations. Firstly, the sample was drawn from one of the best ranked tertiary care level hospital dedicated to Covid-19 patient care, thus limiting the generalization of our findings to hospitals that are less resource rich for catering to covid-19 patients. Comparison of prevalence rates of anxiety, depression, and psychological distress among Covid-19 hospitalized patients in other parts of the country or other countries is worth further investigation. Secondly, in the absence of a comparative group it was difficult comment whether our findings with Covid-19 patients are due to the covid-19 induced mental health impacts. Thirdly, we were also unable to distinguish preexisting mental health conditions from vs Covid-19 induced extra symptoms or rate of aggravation. Fourthly, despite a response rate of 60%, a situation where the non-respondents had higher levels of stress or not at all stressed and therefore not interested in responding in this study can result in some response bias in this study. Fifthly, patients who were screened for anxiety and depression through self-reported tools should also have been clinically evaluated for better diagnostic outcomes.

IMPLICATIONS OF FINDINGS

As India is now globally at number 3 country as per Covid-10 world statistics, our findings will provide vital guidance for the development of a psychological and psychiatric support strategy for hospitals with and without better health care resources. Clinical and policy implications of our study are many. First, health care providers need to identify high-risk groups based on socio-demographic risk factors through baseline screening of anxiety, depression, and psychological distress so as to address for early psychological interventions at the hospital level and even for long-term clinical/research follow up. Our study suggested that female Covid-19 patients had higher psychological distress and at risk of anxiety disorders which partially corresponded to earlier epidemiological findings suggesting women as a higher risk group for depression although in community samples (Lim, 2018).

Secondly, the content of psychological interventions (for example online and offline CBT or Supportive Stress Management Counselling) needs to be modified to suit the needs of the Covid-19 during the epidemic. Customized on

line or telephonic CBT should preferably be delivered to avoid the spread of infection.

Thirdly, all hospitalized Covid-19 patients should be ideally screened for risk to be mentally ill or exacerbation of existing mental illness to provide holistic Covid-care as the fear and apprehension of worsening/death could be severe among them.

CONCLUSION

The study assessed prevalence of anxiety, psychological distress and depression among Covid-19 hospitalized patients in India. The findings suggested the prevalence of anxiety, depression and psychological distress was present in mild to moderate extent among the Covid-19 patients. Patients from low SES, low education level, and low social support were risk factors for poor mental health outcomes. Compulsory screening of mental health during hospital stay of all Covid-19 patients can help in preventing symptoms development or worsening (new or old symptoms) through online psychological and psychiatric interventions. Impact of no financial burden on mental health of Covid-19 hospitalized patients should be explored more in comparative studies where financial burden is involved for Covid-19 treatment.

REFERENCES

- Beusenbergh, M., Orley, J.H., and World Health Organization (1994). A User's guide to the self-reporting questionnaire (SRQ-No. WHO/MNH/PSF/94.8. Unpublished). Geneva: World Health Organization.
- Deshpande, S.N., Sundaram. K.R., and Wig. N.N., (1989). Psychiatric disorders among medical in-patients in an Indian hospital. *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 154, 504-509.
- Dong, Y., Su, T., Jiao, P., Kong, X., Zheng, K., & Tang, M., Kong, F., Zhou, J., Diao, L., & Wu, S. (2020). Prevalence and Factors Associated with Depression and Anxiety of Hospitalized Patients with COVID-*medRxiv* preprint doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.03.24.20043075>; .
- Duncan, L. A., Schaller, M., & Park, J. H., (2009). Perceived vulnerability to disease: Development and validation of a 15-item self-report instrument. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 47(6), 541–546. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2009.05.001>.
- Ellul, M.A., Benjamin, L., Singh, B., Lant, S., Michael, A.V., Easton, A., Kneen, R., Defres, S., Sejvar, J., & Solomon, T. (2020). Neurological associations of COVID-19. *Lancet Neurology*. Published Online July [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422\(20\)30221-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1474-4422(20)30221-0).
- Fernández, R. S., Crivelli, L., Guimet, M.N., Allegri, R.F. & Pedreira, M.E. (2020). Psychological distress associated with COVID-19 quarantine: Latent profile analysis, outcome prediction and mediation analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 277, 75–84.
- Grover, S., Sahoo, S., Mehra, A., Avasthi, A., Tripathi, A., Subramanian, A., et al. (2020). Psychological impact of COVID-19 lockdown: An online survey from India. *Indian J Psychiatry*, 62:354-62.
- Gu, Y., Hu, J., Hu, Y., and et al. (2016). Social supports and mental health: A cross-sectional study on the correlation of self-consistency and congruence in China. *BMC Health Serv Res*; 16:207.
- Guntzviller, L.M., Williamson, L.D., Ratcliff, C.L. (2020). Stress, social support, and mental health among young adult Hispanics. *Fam Community Health*; 43:82e91.
- Hu, Y., Chen, Y, Zheng, Y., You, C., Tan, J., Hu, L., Zhang, Z., and Ding, L. (2020). Factors related to mental health of inpatients with COVID-19 in Wuhan, China. *Brain, Behavior, and Immunity*, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bbi.2020.07.016>
- Huang, Y., Zhao, N. (2020). Generalized anxiety disorder, depressive symptoms and sleep quality during COVID-19 epidemic in China: a

- web-based cross-sectional survey. *Psychiatry Research*. Online published document. <https://doi.org/10.1101/2020.02.19.20025395>.
- Jacobson, N.C., Lord, K.A., Newman, M.G., 2017. Perceived emotional social support in bereaved spouses mediates the relationship between anxiety and depression. *J Affect Disord*; 211:83e91.
- Jianbo, L., Simeng, M., Ying, W., Zhongxiang, C., Jianbo, H., Ning, W., Jiang, W., Hui, D., Tingting, C., Ruiting, L., Huawei, T., Lijun, K., Lihua, Y., Manli, H., Huafen, W., Gaohua, W., Zhongchun, L., and Shaohua, H. (2020). Factors Associated with Mental Health Outcomes Among Health Care Workers Exposed to Coronavirus Disease. *JAMA Network Open.*; 3(3): e203976. doi:10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2020.3976
- Kobayashi, I., Boarts, J.M., Delahanty, D.L. (2007). Polysomnographically measured sleep abnormalities in PTSD: a meta-analytic review. *Psychophysiology* 44, 660-669. doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8986.2007.537.x
- Lee, A.M., Wong, J.G., McAlonan, G.M., et al. (2007). Stress and psychological distress among SARS survivors 1 year after the outbreak. *Can J Psychiatry*.52(4):233-240. doi:10.1177/070674370705200405
- Lee, S.M., Kang, W.S., Cho, A.R., Kim, T., Park, J.K. (2018). Psychological impact of the 2015 MERS outbreak on hospital workers and quarantined hemodialysis patients. *Compr Psychiatry* 87, 123-127. doi: 10.1016/j.comppsy.2018.10.003
- Lim, G.Y. (2014). Prevalence of Depression in the Community from 30 Countries between 1994 and 2014. *Sci. Rep.*2018, 8, 2861. Lu, Y.C., Shu, B.C., Chang, Y.Y., Lung, F.W. (2006). The mental health of hospital workers dealing with severe acute respiratory syndrome. *Psychother Psychosom* 75, 370-375. Doi: 10.1159/000095443
- Mak, I.W., Chu, M.C., Pan, P.C., Yiu, M.G., Chan, V.L. (2009). Long-term psychiatric morbidities among SARS survivors. *Gen Hosp Psychiatry*, 31, 318-326. doi: 10.1016/j.genhosppsych.2009.03.001
- McAlonan, G. M, Lee, A.M., Cheung, V., Cheung, C., Tsang, K.W., Sham, P.C., Chua, S.E., Wong, J.G. (2007). Immediate and sustained psychological impact of an emerging infectious disease outbreak on health care workers. *Can J Psychiatry* 52, 241-247. doi: 10.1177/070674370705200406
- Özdin, Selçuk & Özdin, Şükriye. (2020). Levels and predictors of anxiety, depression and health anxiety during COVID-19 pandemic in Turkish society: The importance of gender. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*. 66. 00276402092705. 10.1177/0020764020927051.
- Pappas, G., Kiriaze, I.J., Giannakis, P., Falagas, M.E. (2009). Psychosocial consequences of infectious diseases. *Clinical Microbiology and Infection*, 15(8), 743-747. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1469-0691.2009.02947.x>.
- Raza, M.R., Shahid, R., Umar, M., Zeb, S., Shehryar, M., Ambreen,S., Ahmed, M., (2020). Assessment of Depression, Anxiety and Stress among Covid-19 Patients by Using DASS 21 Scales. *Journal of Medical Case Reports and Reviews* 3:6 [2020] Available online at: www.jmcrr.info ISSN: [Online] 2589-8655 [Print] 2589-8647.
- Rogers, J.P., Chesney, E., Oliver, D., Pollak, T.A., McGuire, P., Fusar-Poli, P., Zandi, M.S., Lewis, G., David, A.S. (2020). Psychiatric and neuropsychiatric presentations associated with severe coronavirus infections: a systematic review and meta-analysis with comparison to the COVID-19 pandemic. *Lancet Psychiatry* 7:611-27.
- Ropeik, D. (2004). The consequences of fear. *EMBO Reports*, 5(Suppl 1), S56-S60. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sj.embor.7400228>.
- Snaith, R.P., Zigmond, A.S. (1986). The hospital anxiety and depression scale. *Br Med J (Clin Res Ed)*; 292:344.
- Su, T.P., Lien, T.C., Yang, C.Y., Su, Y.L., Wang, J.H., Tsai, S.L., Yin, J.C. (2007). Prevalence of psychiatric morbidity and psychological adaptation of the nurses in a structured SARS caring unit during outbreak: a prospective and periodic assessment study in Taiwan. *J Psychiatr Res*, 41, 119-130. doi: 10.1016/j.jpsychires.2005.12.006.
- The Japan Times, (2020). Japanese official looking after Wuhan returnees found dead. Accessed February 3, 2020. <https://www.japantimes.co.jp/news/2020/02/02/national/crime-legal/japaneseofficial-looking-Wuhan-returnees-found-dead/>.
- Varatharaj, A., Thomas, N., Ellul, M., et al.(2020). UK-wide surveillance of neurological and neuropsychiatric complications of COVID-19: the first 153 patients. *Lancet Psychiatry*; 7: 875– 82; published online May 22. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3601761
- Wang, C., Riyu Pan, Xiaoyang Wan, Yilin Tan, Linkang Xu, Cyrus S. Ho, and Roger C. Ho. (2020b). Immediate Psychological Responses and Associated Factors during the Initial Stage of the 2019. Coronavirus Disease (COVID-19) Epidemic among the General Population in China. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 17, 1729; doi:10.3390/ijerph17051729
- Wang, Y., Di, Y., Ye, J., Wei, W. (2020a). Study on the public psychological states and its related factors during the outbreak of oronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) in some regions of China. *Psychology, Health & Medicine*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2020.1746817>
- Xiao, H., Zhang, Y., Kong, D., et al. (2020). The effects of social support on sleep quality of medical staff treating patients with coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID- 19) in January and February 2020 in China. *Med Sci Monit*;26: e923549.
- Yancy, C.W., (2020). COVID-19 and African Americans. *JAMA*; published online April 15. DOI:10.1001/jama.2020.6548. Zimet, G.D., Dahlem, N.W., Zimet, S.G., Farley G.K. (1988). The Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support. *Journal of Personality Assessment*; 52:30-41